

**IMPROVEMENT OF THE UNIT FOR FILLING JOINTS, CRACKS
OF ROAD COVERINGS.**

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Annotation: This article considers ways to improve the aggregate for pouring joints and cracks in asphalt concrete pavement, expansion joints in cement concrete pavement, reducing financial costs and minimizing human participation in repair work. Various reasons for the appearance of cracks on the road surface are listed. A review of the existing pavement seam fillers is made.

The main result of the study is the development of a trailed aggregate for a pavement joint filler, which can sequentially perform the following operations: filling cracks with asphalt concrete pavement bitumen, filling expansion joints with cement concrete pavement bitumen mastic, cleaning asphalt concrete pavement cracks from dirt, dust, moisture with compressed air.

Key words: project, equipment, repair, cracks, road surface, quality, method, economy.

Introduction. Sealing cracks in asphalt concrete is one of the important operations of repair and restoration work to keep the road surface in a safe condition. This operation prevents precipitation, salts and various reagents from penetrating deep into the layers of the road surface through cracks, which can lead to damage to the surface of the road surface and to dangerous changes in the lower layers of the pavement.

The sealing operation, as a rule, consists in filling cracks with hot bituminous mastic using joint fillers (melting pots). There are certain technological and technical requirements for the equipment used - maintaining a constant high temperature of bituminous mastic, because loss of operating temperature entails a

decrease in its adhesive and other properties. The heating method is also important, it should exclude direct contact of the burner flame with the mastic.

There are various reasons for the appearance of cracks in the road surface:

1. Due to thermal deformation, shrinkage of the pavement;
2. Due to natural aging and low bitumen content, the elasticity of the road surface decreases;
3. Shifts of pavement layers due to insufficient connection between them.

To the listed reasons, we can add the following factors, which can also be the reasons for the formation of cracks in road surfaces:

- 1) the paving was laid in conditions that violate the temperature and humidity conditions;
- 2) in the manufacture of asphalt concrete mixtures, deviations were made in the ratio of filler / bitumen, the presence of contamination (for example, dirty crushed stone was used);
- 3) there were violations in the technologies of laying and compacting the top layer of the road surface;
- 4) during the construction of the subgrade, violations of the requirements for compaction of the lower layers of the road pavement were allowed;
- 5) low-quality repair and restoration work was carried out to seal cracks in the upper layers of the road surface.

It is known that cracks can be repaired and not repaired by the method of their sealing.

Repaired cracks include longitudinal cracks. Their formation may be preceded by the appearance of fatigue cracks, especially if two or more cracks are present on the track. This problem is usually attributed to either shrinkage of the asphalt pavement or insufficient sealing of the joints of adjacent paver passes.

Longitudinal cracks are eliminated by sealing them with a melting and pouring machine.

Transverse cracks are formed on the asphalt concrete pavement at right angles to the longitudinal cracks and are the result of soil shrinkage under the roadway. Transverse cracks are not dangerous if their number is small. These cracks are also mainly eliminated by the method of their sealing. Reflection cracks occur mainly on pavements if existing cracks in the underlying pavement have not been repaired before laying the new pavement, which are reflected at the top of the surface over time.

Group cracks - this type of crack creates areas with cracks overlapping each other at different angles. One of the reasons for the appearance of group cracks is the lack of constant traffic, which, as it were, “massages” the coating, giving it elasticity. Other reasons may be technological violations in the production of asphalt mixes at the plant.

If the repair is carried out in the initial period of the appearance of group cracks, then only their sealing can be dispensed with, but if the process is started, then a complete repair of the damaged area will be required.

Cracks, the repair of which is not possible by the method of their sealing, include fatigue and shear.

Fig.1. Shear cracks.

Fatigue cracks - the cause of their appearance is the natural aging of the material of the upper layer of the pavement, which ultimately leads to fatigue cracking. The top layer of the road section with fatigue cracks must be removed and then replaced. Edge cracks have, as it were, crescent-shaped shapes that intersect the edges of the pavement and are located at a distance of approximately 0.5 m from the edge of the pavement adjacent to the dirt shoulder. They are caused by overloading the edge of the road surface, the destruction or weakening of the shoulder. It is not advisable to repair such cracks with the help of sealing; they need to be removed and a new material of the top layer of the road surface applied.

Shear cracks - cracks form a characteristic crescent shape (fig. 1) and are the result of the "separation" of the upper layer of the asphalt concrete pavement from the underlying layers due to large displacements or poor communication between the layers. In this situation, sealing these cracks by sealing them is also not only inefficient, but also useless.

Technological features of the repair of cracks by the method of their sealing. Preparation of asphalt for sealing.

Proper preparation of cracks for their sealing is very important in the technological process of repairing the top layer of the pavement. It begins with blowing the cracks with an air stream, for example, with air knives, to clean them from dust, dirt or pieces of destroyed pavement material. It is acceptable to use more powerful air compressors when cleaning cracks to remove large fragments, debris and moisture from cracks.

Crack cutting, using a joint cutter, is recommended to ensure the required degree of bituminous emulsion filling of cracks in the asphalt concrete pavement. An insufficient amount of bituminous emulsion will not be able to provide the necessary protective effect against water penetration, which is the main cause of destruction of the pavement surface.

To ensure reliable adhesion and complete filling of cracks in the asphalt concrete pavement, the applied repair material is heated to the temperature recommended by its manufacturer in an oil-jacketed heating melting pot.

Overview of existing joint fillers.

Seam fillers are designed for heating and applying hot sealants (polymer-bitumen and rubber-bitumen mastics) when performing work on filling cracks and joints in asphalt concrete and cement concrete pavements.

The joint filler is designed for heating and supplying bitumen-elastomer sealing mastics under pressure when performing work on sealing cracks, joints and waterproofing during repair and construction work on roads, airfield pavements, bridges, overpasses.

CRAFCO Super Shot Series Jointers are machines with a fully automatic workflow control system. The heating of mastic in the boiler occurs due to indirect heating of the boiler (oil jacket). The automated system allows you to set and maintain the required (optimal) temperature of the material and thermal oil. All parameters are displayed digitally on the control panel.

Rice. 2. CRAFCO joint fillers.

The electrically heated hose allows mastic to be applied, eliminating its hardening in the supply line, which greatly facilitates the work of the operator. If the hose or material has not reached the required temperature, the system will not automatically start the feed pump in order to exclude the possibility of a technological error (human factor). The most efficient operation of the machines is facilitated by the absence of lines under constant pressure. There are also no valves and the number of moving parts is kept to a minimum. Preparation of the installation for operation takes about 45 minutes. The SuperShot grouter is available in 227 and 473 liter boiler capacities, with a choice of various additional options (compressor, self-propelled front wheel drive). Benefits of Super Shot

- Electric heating of the hose and applicator to the very tip (24V);
- There are no taps and valves in the mastic supply line;
- Supply of mastic by a high-capacity pump, supply adjustment by a potentiometer;
- One type of burner fuel and drive motor (diesel), except for SS60 (propane).

Seam fillers ED-135 are widely used for sealing expansion joints with bituminous mastics on cement concrete and asphalt concrete pavements of roads, runways and aprons and other elements of flat infrastructure at airfields, in addition to waterproofing foundations and roofs of buildings.

Rice. 1. General view of the filler.

1-coupling device; 2-parking wheel; 3-compressor; 4-engine; 5-fuel tank; 6-bar mastic dispensing sleeve; 7-loading hatch with a tank; 8-activator; 9-rod; 10-mixer hydraulic distributor; 11-slide damper; 12-box for spare parts; 13 purge fitting; 14-box for batteries; 15-overrun brake; 16-hydraulic pump; 17-burner; 18-drive agitator; 19-mastic pump drive; 20-wardrobe; 21-tank; 22-hydraulic tank; 23 parking wheel.

Boiler pourer ED-135 has a number of advantages and disadvantages:

The boiler is self-propelled due to the presence of a hydraulic drive to the front wheel;

Using a thermal jacket (heat carrier volume - 125 l of thermal oil) around the boiler perimeter for indirect and uniform mastic melting inside the tank;

The presence of a vertical agitator with a hydraulic drive inside the tank;

Sufficiently high thermal insulation along the contour of the boiler;

Reliable 23 hp diesel engine.

Seam filler ZSH-4. The main element of the pourer is a cylindrical heating tank with a vertical axis. Warming up the mastic to the operating temperature is carried out using a diesel burner through an oil jacket filled with thermal oil. The supply of heated mastic is carried out through a supply hose and a fishing rod, with a non-submersible bitumen pump.

The bitumen pump does not have a heating jacket; it, together with the supply rod, supply hose and piping system, is located in a thermally insulated cabinet and is heated by air heated by the gas outlet pipe of the fuel burner.

The hydraulic system has two independent circuits - agitator drive hydraulic motor and a bitumen pump drive hydraulic motor. The main elements of the hydraulic system are a tandem hydraulic pump and a two-section hydraulic distributor with built-in safety valves.

The machine is operated in the temperature range from plus 5°C to plus

40°C.

The pourer is equipped with two easily removable nozzles - for filling joints and for filling cracks.

Advantages:

- autonomy (no binding to the carrier / tractor);
- Honda GX630 engine (gasoline, 2-cylinder, power, hp - 20.8 (kW 15.5));
- PZhD-600 heater (diesel);
- reinforced design of the paddle mixer (with reverse);
- bitumen pump (non-submersible type);
- the presence of a thermal cabinet;
- the presence of a hydraulic line for connecting an additional hydraulic tool;
- the material is heated through an oil jacket.

Rice. 3. Joint filler ZSh-4.

Material and methods. The trailed joint filler is developed on the basis of a 2-axle trailer 2PRShch-4.8. The main technological units and assemblies of the trailed joint filler being developed include:

- container for bituminous mastic and their components;
- bituminous mastic heating system: gas burner and gas cylinders;

- bitumen mastic supply system: unit for mixing bitumen and rubber crumb, compressor, receivers and pipelines;
- drive units: gearboxes, hydraulic motors, hydraulic pumps transmission mechanism (chain and belt);
- base tractor wheeled tractor TTZ-100.

To heat bituminous mastic, a heating system has been developed, which includes a special gas heating system, through gas burners GKS-2.5.

In the set of the joint filler unit, containers for bitumen emulsion are provided for wetting the edge of the asphalt concrete pavement when eliminating cracks.

The joint filler unit is equipped with unified units for driving existing gearboxes, a compressor for the pneumatic system of the main tank. Usually bituminous mastic gives in under pressure approximately 2...2,5 kg/cm³.

Belt and chain drives, worm and bevel gears, etc. were used.

Joint fillers and boilers for heating bituminous material on the construction market are available in large numbers and in a wide variety of modifications and types.

All of the equipment listed above are separate working units. This significantly complicates and increases the cost of repair and restoration work, since a large amount of various equipment has to be purchased and transported to work sites. Thus, it is economically and technologically expedient to develop a trailed joint filler unit that performs the main working functions in the complex when sealing cracks and expansion joints in the road surface.

The essence and content of the study.

The durability of pavement operation depends on the quality and timely repair and restoration work.

The essence of the study is to develop a trailed pavement joint filler that can perform the following pavement repair operations: cleaning from dirt and

moisture by blowing with compressed air, filling cracks with bitumen, filling expansion joints of cement concrete pavement with bitumen mastic.

To perform the above technological operations, a project of a trailed joint filler is proposed (Fig. 4), which will combine several devices.

A 2-axle tractor trailer 2PTS-4.5 is offered as a base vehicle. To deliver this unit, T-80 tractors can be used. To fill road pavement joints, the proposed unit is equipped with a hydraulic motor to transmit rotation to the gearbox and compressor. The cleaned crack is filled with bituminous mixture through a bitumen nozzle.

Rice. Fig. 4. Profile and frontal view of a trailed pavement joint filler.

Calculations of the economic feasibility of this project were carried out by comparing the proposed unit with existing sets of equipment for repairing pavement cracks.

Performance calculations also confirmed that the proposed unit is more efficient than the combined use of the above equipment.

Conclusion.

Thus, the practical application of the equipment proposed in the article minimizes manual labor and the amount of various equipment involved in the

technological process of crack repair as a whole. Minimization of manual labor during repair and restoration work ensures an improvement in the quality of their implementation. Accordingly, the number of people in the repair teams is decreasing. The need to attract additional machinery and equipment is minimized. Reduced work time. At the same time, the productivity and efficiency of the repair teams are increasing. The terms of non-repair operation of road surfaces are also increasing due to the improvement of the quality of repair work. Therefore, the development and practical implementation in the road construction industry of the developed equipment for the repair of road surfaces is economically and technically feasible.

References:

1. V.I. Balovnev, G. Kustarev and others. Road-building machines and complexes. Publishing house "Sibadi". Moscow. Omsk. 2001. 522 st.
2. Maksudov Z.T., Kудaybergenov M, Ismailov J. On the frequency of service maintenance of the "SHANTUI SD 32" bulldozer in terms of fuel consumption and machine production, Collection of scientific papers of the eighth international scientific-practical conference, pp.151 -154, Almaty, (2019).
3. K.J.Rustamov, S.I. Komilov, M.S. Kудaybergenov, Sh.X.Shermatov, Sh.Sh. Xudoyqulov. Experimental Study of Hydraulic Equipment Operation Process. Construction Mechanics, Hydraulics and Water Resources Engineering. pages 5, 2021-year. <http://conmechhydro.tech/>.
4. Maksudov Z.T., Kудaybergenov M.S., Ernazarov J.Z. Methods of determining the number of road vehicles when forming a set of machines. International Scientific and Practical Conference "Actual Issues of Science". - 12345678, 2022. 10.528.
5. Maksudov Z.T., Kудaybergenov M.S. Modeling of a set of machines. Eurasian journal of mathematical theory and computer sciences. Issue 14, December 2022 ISSN 2181-2861 Page 10.

6. Dovgyalo V.A. Machines and equipment for the maintenance of highways: textbook. allowance / V.A. Dovgyalo; M-in transp. and communications Rep. Belarus, Belarus. state transp. - Gomel: BelSUT, 2016. - 288 p.

7. Zokir Maksudov*, Mavlyan Kudaybergenov , Sh Kabikenov and Aydana Sungatollakzy. The machines optimal set development for the construction of automotive roads elements based on the "Norm" for machines employment cost. Tashkent State University of Transport. E3S Web of Conferences 264, 02031 (2021) <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202126402031> CONMECHYDRO - 2021.

8. Kudaybergenov M.S., Mukhamedova N.B., Mirkholikov S.M., Yusubjonov S.S. Increased teeth performance excavator buckets. Eurasian journal of academic research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5584563>.

